

Preparation and Antibacterial Activity of 2-Phenyl-3-(2',4'-diarylamino-s-triazin-6-yl)-5/H/CH₃-carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinone and 2-Aryl-3-(*p*-aminosulphophenyl/2'-pyrimidylaminosulphophenyl)-*p*-carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinones

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Some new 4-thiazolidinones have been prepared from the Schiff's bases obtained from 2,4-diarylamino-6-amino-*s*-triazine, sulphanilamide and sulphapyridine. The constitution of the product was supported by ir spectra. The products were tested for antimicrobial activity.

4-THIAZOLIDINONES possess biological activity, like hypnotics¹, anaesthetic², antifungal³, etc. *s*-Triazine derivatives also possess anticancer⁴, antimalarial⁵ and antiviral⁶ activity. With a view to synthesise more active drugs, we have synthesised 4-thiazolidinone of types 1 and 2, having *s*-triazine moiety. Sulphonamide group 2,4-diarylamino-6-chloro-*s*-triazines were treated with liquor ammonia at 80° to get 2,4-diarylamino-6-amino-*s*-triazine which were reacted with benzaldehyde to yield Schiff bases. The Schiff bases were then condensed with thioglycolic and thiomalic acids to obtain 4-thiazolidinones.

The products were screened for antibacterial activity⁷. The ir spectra (KBr) of 2-phenyl-3-(2',4'-di-*o*-nitroanilino-*s*-triazine-6-yl)-4-thiazolidinone⁸ showed bands at 810 (C₈N₈), 1 680 (C—O), 1 580 (—CO—N) and 3 200 cm⁻¹ (NH).

R = Aryl, R' = H or carboxymethyl

R = aryl or H

Considerable interest has been shown in the chemistry of sulphonamides due to their uses as antibacterial, anticancer, antimalarial, antifungal, herbicidal, insecticidal and pesticidal properties^{9,10}. With a view to prepare better therapeutic agents, we have prepared 2-aryl-3-(*p*-aminosulphophenyl/2'-pyrimidylaminosulphophenyl)-5-carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinone (2) by condensing thiomalic acid with Schiff's bases^{11,12} obtained from different aromatic aldehydes with sulphanilamide or sulphadiazine.

The constitution of the product¹³ was supported by ir spectra (KBr). They showed the characteristic bands at 1 180 (—SO₂—), 1 300 (—SO₂—N—), 1 660 (—CH—N—), 1 600 (—N—C) and 1 430 cm⁻¹ (C—O stretch carboxylic acid). The products were screened for antibacterial activity.

Experimental

2,4-Diphenylaminobenzalamino-*s*-triazines: Benzaldehyde (0.01 mol) was dissolved in ethanol (95%; 20 ml) and was added to 2,4-dianilino-6-amino-*s*-triazine (0.01 mol) dissolved in ethanol (95%; 20 ml) and refluxed on a water-bath for 2 h. The product was isolated and crystallised from ethanol, (92%), m.p. 132° (Found: C, 72.20; H, 4.85; N, 22.85. C₂₂H₁₈N₆ calcd. for: C, 72.13; H, 4.91; N, 22.45%).

Similarly, other *s*-triazine derivatives were condensed with benzaldehyde (Table 1).

2-Phenyl-3-(2',4'-phenylamino-*s*-triazin-6-yl)-4-thiazolidinones: 2,4-Phenylamino-6-benzalamino-*s*-triazine (0.01 mol) was dissolved in benzene (25 ml), and thioglycolic acid (0.01 mol) dissolved in benzene (10 ml) was added to this solution and refluxed on a water-bath for 4 h. The product was isolated

and crystallised from ethanol, (88%), m.p. 178° (Found : C, 65.40 ; H, 4.50 ; N, 19.0. $C_{22}H_{20}ON_6S$ calcd. for : C, 65.45 ; H, 4.54 ; N, 19.08%).

Similarly, thiomalic acid was condensed. The physical and analytical data are recorded in Table 2.

2-Phenyl-3-(2',4'-phenylamino-s-triazin-6-yl)-5-carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinones : 2,4-Diphenylamino-

6-benzalamino-s-triazine (0.01 mol) was condensed with thiomalic acid (0.01 mol) in presence of anhydrous zinc chloride (0.5 g) at 160° for 2 h. The temperature was then raised to 180° for 30 min. The product was dissolved in sodium bicarbonate solution and reprecipitated with acid and crystallised from ethanol (Found : C, 75.25 ; H, 4.36 ; N, 16.80. $C_{26}H_{22}O_8N_6S$ calcd. for : C, 75.70 ; H,

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF 2,4-DIARYLAMINO-6-BENZALAMINO-S-TRIAZINES

Sl. no.	R	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Yield %	Nitrogen % : Found/(Calcd.)
1.	Phenyl	$C_{22}H_{18}N_6$	132	92	22.85 (22.95)
2.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	$C_{24}H_{22}N_6$	140	62	21.20 (21.32)
3.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	$C_{24}H_{22}N_6$	110	60	21.14 (21.32)
4.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	$C_{24}H_{22}N_6$	180	65	21.16 (21.32)
5.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	$C_{22}H_{16}N_6Cl_2$	165	63	19.15 (19.31)
6.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	$C_{22}H_{16}N_6Cl_2$	190	66	18.11 (19.21)
7.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	$C_{22}H_{16}N_6O_4$	200	66	24.60 (24.56)
8.	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	$C_{24}H_{22}O_2N_6$	182	64	19.63 (19.72)
9.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	$C_{24}H_{22}O_2N_6$	95	67	19.60 (19.72)
10.	<i>o</i> -Nitrophenyl	$C_{22}H_{16}O_4N_6$	205	72	24.20 (24.56)
11.	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	$C_{22}H_{16}O_4N_6$	195	70	24.15 (24.56)
12.	α -Naphthyl	$C_{20}H_{14}N_6$	100	66	17.90 (18.03)
13.	<i>p</i> -Carboxyphenyl	$C_{24}H_{18}O_4N_6$	275	67	18.15 (18.26)

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF 4-THIAZOLIDINONES (1)

Sl. no.	R	R'	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Yield %	Nitrogen % : Found/(Calcd.)
1.	Phenyl	H	$C_{24}H_{20}N_6OS$	178	88	19.00 (19.09)
2.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	H	$C_{26}H_{18}N_6OS$	180	80	18.20 (17.95)
3.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	H	$C_{26}H_{18}N_6OS$	110	75	18.30 (17.95)
4.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	H	$C_{26}H_{18}N_6OS$	220	78	18.27 (17.95)
5.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	H	$C_{24}H_{16}N_6OSCl_2$	156	82	16.40 (16.50)
6.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	H	$C_{24}H_{16}N_6OSCl_2$	154	86	16.40 (16.50)
7.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	H	$C_{24}H_{14}N_6O_5S$	160	87	21.05 (21.13)
8.	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	H	$C_{26}H_{18}N_6O_2S$	200	80	16.70 (16.80)
9.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	H	$C_{26}H_{18}N_6O_2S$	110	84	16.72 (16.80)
10.	<i>o</i> -Nitrophenyl	H	$C_{24}H_{14}N_6O_5S$	180	85	21.00 (21.13)
11.	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	H	$C_{24}H_{14}N_6O_5S$	240	82	21.10 (21.13)
12.	α -Naphthyl	H	$C_{22}H_{14}N_6OS$	250	70	19.60 (19.71)
13.	<i>p</i> -Carboxyphenyl	H	$C_{26}H_{18}O_5N_6$	162	72	21.15 (21.21)

(Table 2 contd.)

14.	Phenyl	CH ₃	C ₂₅ H ₂₂ N ₆ O ₈ S	180	87	18.00 (18.50)
15.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	CH ₃	C ₂₇ H ₂₄ N ₆ O ₈ S	140	85	17.40 (17.42)
16.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	CH ₃	C ₂₇ H ₂₄ N ₆ O ₈ S	120	77	17.45 (17.42)
17.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	CH ₃	C ₂₇ H ₂₄ N ₆ O ₈ S	225	79	17.35 (17.42)
18.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	OH	C ₂₅ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₈ Cl ₂	170	72	16.00 (16.06)
19.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	OH	C ₂₅ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₈ Cl ₂	165	78	16.20 (16.06)
20.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	OH	C ₂₅ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₈ S	167	80	21.87 (21.99)
21.	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	OH	C ₂₇ H ₂₀ N ₆ O ₈ S	205	70	16.40 (16.34)
22.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	OH	C ₂₇ H ₂₀ N ₆ O ₈ S	115	74	16.20 (16.34)
23.	<i>o</i> -Nitrophenyl	OH	C ₂₅ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₈ S	190	75	21.82 (21.99)
24.	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	OH	C ₂₅ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₈ S	230	70	21.87 (21.99)
25.	α -Naphthyl	OH	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₈ S	240	80	15.10 (15.16)
26.	<i>p</i> -Carboxyphenyl	CH ₃	C ₂₇ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₆	180	78	16.40 (17.47)
27.	Phenyl	CH ₂ COOH	C ₂₅ H ₂₂ N ₆ O ₈ S	145	50	16.80 (16.86)
28.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	CH ₂ COOH	C ₂₇ H ₂₄ N ₆ O ₈ S	155	52	16.00 (15.96)
29.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	CH ₂ COOH	C ₂₇ H ₂₄ N ₆ O ₈ S	161-2	54	16.00 (15.96)
30.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	CH ₂ COOH	C ₂₇ H ₂₄ N ₆ O ₈ S	167	58	16.00 (15.96)
31.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	CH ₂ COOH	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ Cl ₂ N ₆ O ₈ S	195-6	61	14.85 (14.81)
32.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	CH ₂ COOH	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ Cl ₂ N ₆ O ₈ S	191	63	14.85 (14.81)
33.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	CH ₂ COOH	C ₂₅ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₈ S	210	55	19.20 (19.05)
34.	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	CH ₂ COOH	C ₂₇ H ₂₀ N ₆ O ₈ S	141	49	15.00 (15.05)
35.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	CH ₂ COOH	C ₂₇ H ₂₀ N ₆ O ₈ S	150	52	15.00 (15.05)
36.	<i>o</i> -Nitrophenyl	CH ₂ COOH	C ₂₅ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₈ S	190	52	18.85 (19.05)
37.	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	CH ₂ COOH	C ₂₅ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₈ S	195	50	18.90 (19.05)
38.	α -Naphthyl	CH ₂ COOH	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₈ S	180	52	12.80 (12.37)
39.	<i>p</i> -Carboxyphenyl	CH ₂ COOH	C ₂₇ H ₂₂ N ₆ O ₈ S	190	53	14.80 (14.35)

4.41; N, 16.86%). The physical and analytical data are presented in Table 2.

Benzalaminobenzenesulphonamide: Benzaldehyde (0.01 mol) in ethanol (95%; 10 ml) was added to sulphamylamide (0.01 mol) in ethanol (95%; 25 ml) and refluxed on a water-bath at 70-80° for 2 h. The resulting mixture was poured into crushed ice. The product was isolated and crystallised from ethanol, (72%), m.p. 175° (lit. 176°).

2-Phenyl-3-(*p*-aminosulphophenyl)-5-carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinones: Benzalsulphanilamide (0.01 mol) was condensed with thiomalic acid (0.01 mol) in presence of anhydrous zinc chloride (0.5 g) at 160° for 2 h. The temperature was then raised to 180° for 30 min. The products was dissolved in sodium bicarbonate solution, reprecipitated with acid and

crystallised from ethanol, (62%), m.p. 125° (Found: C, 52, H, 4, N, 7.19. C₁₇H₁₆N₂O₂S₂ calcd. for: C, 52.04, H, 4.08; N, 7.14%).

Similarly, other substituted Schiff bases were treated with thiomalic acid. The physical and analytical data are recorded in Table 3.

Antibacterial activity: Testing of antibacterial activity of different compounds was carried out by disk method⁷ using ethanol as a solvent at a concentration of 10 mg ml⁻¹; test solution contained 0.5 mg. All the compounds showed high activity against *S. aureus* and good activity against *E. coli*.

In case of *s*-triazine derivatives, the antimicrobial activity of the Schiff bases and 5/H/CH₃-4-thiazoli-

TABLE 3—2-ARYL-3-(*p*-AMINOSULPHOPHENYL)/2'-PYRIMIDYLAMINOSULPHOPHENYL)-5-CARBOXYMETHYL-4-THIAZOLIDINONES

Sl. no.	R	R ₁	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Yield %	Nitrogen % : Found/(Calcd.)
1.	Phenyl	H	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₆ S ₂	125	62	7.19 (7.14)
2.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	H	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₆ S ₂	121	61	6.81 (6.86)
3.	<i>m</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	H	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₆ S ₂	210	58	6.81 (6.86)
4.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	H	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₆ S ₂	220	64	6.81 (6.86)
5.	3-Bromo-2-hydroxyphenyl	H	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ BrN ₂ O ₆ S ₂	195	69	5.71 (5.74)
6.	3,5-Dibromo-2-hydroxyphenyl	H	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₆ S ₂	117	71	4.91 (4.94)
7.	4-Hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl	H	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₇ S ₂	110	65	6.35 (6.39)
8.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	H	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ ClN ₂ O ₆ S ₂	116-7	55	6.55 (6.56)
9.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	H	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ ClN ₂ O ₆ S ₂	115	63	6.51 (6.56)
10.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	H	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₆ S ₂	180	59	7.10 (7.17)
11.	Phenyl	2-Pyrimidyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₆ S ₂	265	58	11.90 (11.91)
12.	<i>m</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	2-Pyrimidyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₆ S ₂	182	55	11.50 (11.52)
13.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	2-Pyrimidyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₆ S ₂	235	63	11.50 (11.52)
14.	3,5-Dibromo-2-hydroxyphenyl	2-Pyrimidyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ Br ₂ N ₄ O ₆ S ₂	110	67	8.60 (8.69)
15.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	2-Pyrimidyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ ClN ₄ O ₆ S ₂	117	62	11.001 (11.10)
16.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	2-Pyrimidyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ ClN ₄ O ₆ S ₂	180	66	11.011 (11.10)
17.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	2-Pyrimidyl	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₆ S ₂	175	61	11.11 (11.20)

dinones is identical. The diameter of zone of inhibition varies from 19 to 30 mm. 5-Carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinones are more active as compared to 4-thiazolidinones, *m*-, *p*-tolyl, *m*-, *p*-chlorophenyl, *p*-nitrophenyl derivatives showing better activity. The diameter of zone of inhibition varies from 30 to 35 mm. In case of sulphonamides when R₁=2-pyridylamino and R=phenyl, *m*-, *p*-hydroxyphenyl, 3,5-dibromo-2-hydroxyphenyl, the diameter of zone inhibition varies from 40 to 46 mm.

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